

THE ROLE OF MENTOR-STUDENT RELATIONSHIP IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNERS

Yakhyaeva Lobarkhon Khabibulla qizi

MA Student, Tashkent branch of MSU named after M.V. Lomonosov

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Education has taken on a greater significance in today's expanding society and has a profound effect on many facets of individuals' lives. Accordingly, providing learning resources like textbooks, teaching aids, and pedagogical instructions is only one aspect of great education; another is mentorship in all facets of the academic journey, from elementary school to tertiary education.

We can all agree without a doubt that mentoring is related to every area of life where people want to develop and interact with others. Mentoring helps novice teachers advance their careers, develop their personalities, and increase their knowledge, according to several studies. A mentor is someone who provides career counseling, behavior management, social relationship development, self-esteem enhancement, and independence attributes to mentees. A mentor can be a parent, friend, family member, teacher, or neighbor. This underlines that a mentor should always be willing to engage with mentees in an effective manner in order to facilitate appropriate guidance. Additionally, a mentor should feel free to be approachable in person in order to provide the necessary information and expertise for people who need to develop specific areas of knowledge in a variety of domains.

One of the most important things in helping people realize their full potential is mentoring. A mentor plays a vital role in helping someone grow and develop their life skills and career-related competences, as well as helping them make personal changes and improve their chances of getting hired. A mentor fosters healthy connections between mentees, which enhances their capacity for self-awareness, interaction, and decision-making.

The study's objective was to comprehend the function and significance of mentoring in students' professional development, academic achievement, and personal improvement while studying in higher education institutions.

A mentee should be coachable and open to learning, while a mentor should offer direction and encouragement. A mentee should also be courteous, able to receive criticism well, and open-minded. Most essential, confidentiality should be upheld by both the mentor and the mentee. Mutual respect, trust, and a shared dedication to learning are the foundations of a successful mentor-mentee relationship. Relationships where both sides have an equal stake in the mentee's success are the best.

In order to wrap up a mentor session, mentees should summarize the key points that were discussed. In addition to letting the mentor and mentee create an action plan to build momentum for their next meeting, this lets the mentor know that the mentee was paying attention. After that, the mentee ought to thank the mentor via email, provide a synopsis of the meeting, and outline the actions they will take going forward. Once more, these email summaries serve as a means of demonstrating to a mentor that a mentee was paying attention as well as creating an activity log that can be consulted at a later time. Lastly, an update on the status of the action items should be given before the next mentor session starts. This demonstrates to the mentor once more that the mentee paid attention and followed any advice. Successful relationships between mentors and mentees are characterized by excellent communication and advancement. Communicate, send, and

follow up with an update after sharing the review to make sure that there is progress and communication.

Both the mentor and the mentee need to be accomplished educators. By this, it means that a mentor should be able to provide useful guidance in addition to acting as a positive role model. A mentee should also be eager to learn and open to guidance. The mentor's counsel must be taken seriously and used consistently. The mentee must allow the shared insight to settle before putting it into practice. Since the mentor-mentee relationship is based on give and take, having these qualities or well-defined roles is essential to its success.

It is crucial that the mentee contact a mentor with a very specific skill set in mind for them to learn. For instance, having a mentor in business is not sufficient in and of itself. As the mentee, you should have unwavering focus. Moreover, if you want to grow your negotiation skills, approach a mentor who has strong negotiation skills within your industry.

It's critical for the mentor to clarify the nature of the partnership. Make sure that the advice you give the mentee is practical and based on what they need to learn. Finally, to maintain the relationship, make sure the meetings are consistent—that is, once a month.

Aspiring mentors prioritize assisting their mentees in reaching their objectives, whether they are seeking a mentor themselves or are interested in becoming one. While mentors have various duties, their ultimate aim is to assist their mentee in achieving their goals. One of the duties of a mentor is to offer support, direction, feedback, and advise to the mentee. In addition, you act as their ally, sponsor, advocate, counselor, adviser, teacher, and role model. You'll provide them every resource they need to grow into better versions of themselves.

A mentee should always be willing to listen, and a mentor should lead by example. The key to a successful mentor/mentee relationship is engagement. A mentor must help their mentee discover their creative instinct because a mentee wants to know not only how, but why. The mentee should be receptive to hearing about and investigating fresh, imaginative ideas at the same time. In the end, both the mentor and the mentee can gain something from the experience as this fosters a degree of trust between them.

Mentors should take on the position of devil's advocate among many other things, and mentees should constantly question and challenge their mentors with thought-provoking, open-ended questions — all done with respect, of course. For instance, mentors should try their best to offer counterarguments or novel ideas when the mentee approaches them with an idea or thought. Because they are compelled to consider not just what they believe would work but also what others might say to diminish their ideas, this helps the mentee grow faster. Simultaneously, the mentee ought to endeavor to comprehend every facet of the mentor's knowledge, regardless of the topic, in order to eventually become an advocate for themselves. Paradoxically, this fosters personal development for each of them, strengthening their bond and maybe enhancing the information they can impart to others.

Since mentoring involves the transmission of knowledge, it is essential that the mentor understands the mentee's preferred learning style and knows how to provide learning opportunities that suit it. The mentee-centered approach is essential for learning to occur, i.e., getting to know your mentee beyond the learning style; mentors should promote a laid-back, yet productive environment and use active listening skills. This not only advances the mentoring's objective but also fosters rapport and trust, both of which improve the quality of the connection between the mentor and the mentee as a whole.

It is the duty of both the mentor and the mentee to provide feedback to one another. The mentor must ascertain whether the mentee is taking in the advice they are giving them and whether it is helping the mentee expand their knowledge and comprehension. Simultaneously, the mentor ought to provide the mentee with feedback regarding their comprehension of the development that is being made and whether the advice is being followed as intended. Both sides are able to prepare for the next stage of development and open up new options to explore by being honest about how they feel the relationship is going.

Following through is one of a mentee's responsibilities. No matter how great the mentor's advice is, it is useless if it is not followed! Likewise, it is essential that a mentor customize stated counsel for every customer. While giving general advice could seem easier, a shrewd mentor will take the time to get to know each mentee so that she can determine how best to modify her recommendations.

It is important to "core values sharing" as one of the many duties that a mentor and mentee share. Their relationship takes a big turn for the better once they are in agreement on fundamental principles. Otherwise, it practically prevents that development when one side contains values that are incompatible.

Every instructor and every student in formal education has to receive mentoring. Good mentorship encourages students' overall development and progress. Students do not, however, understand the value and necessity of mentoring for their academic, professional, and personal growth. Because of this, the study has made the students aware of the fact that mentoring is an art form that helps mentees discover their true selves as well as their hidden skills and abilities. Furthermore, it helped them realize that mentorship facilitates teachers' acquisition of valuable expertise in related sectors. Students, organizations, and professionals themselves might all benefit directly from it. To put it another way, mentoring assists both professors and students in gaining in-depth knowledge of a variety of subjects, which benefits both parties when it comes to helping students plan their future academic endeavors. Mentors offer a supportive relationship that is centered on the professional and academic progress and accomplishments of their students. This relationship has the potential to generate numerous good outcomes related to academics, careers, and psychological well-being.

Teachers ought to volunteer to be mentors; students who studied overseas and working teachers should serve as role models for other educators in the practice of mentoring. Teachers shouldn't view mentorships as an added load or additional responsibility. To evaluate the actual state of mentorship in government schools and universities, another study might be carried out. Students ought to regularly attend their mentors looking for assistance with all things connected to individual, scholarly, and occupational evolution. Effective mentoring is required for advantages for the pupils. Students need to accept accountability for their own growth and learning with the assistance of a competent guide.

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